

**93rd Annual Meeting of the German
Society of Glass Technology (DGG) in
conjunction with the
French Union for Science and Glass
Technology (USTV) Annual Meeting
Nürnberg, Germany**

13. - 15. May 2019

Abstracts

Deutsche
Glastechnische Gesellschaft e. V.

Contents

FunGlass	8
FunGlass Centre: progress of a successful international Centre in the field of functional glasses.....	9
Design of sol-gel media and inkjet printing of mullite	10
Sol-gel derived ion-doped mesoporous bioactive glasses for biomedical applications.....	11
Additive manufacturing of akermanite glass-ceramic scaffolds with hierarchical porosity	13
Improvement of corrosion behavior of aluminium and magnesium alloys by graphene based hybrid silica sol-gel coatings	14
High temperature properties / Hot forming, secondary manufacturing, Link Properties structure / Mechanic of Glass	15
Mechanical properties and bonding in phospho-aluminosilicate glasses.....	16
Pressure-induced densification of vitreous silica: insight from elastic properties.....	17
Cooling rate and reactivity of granulated blast furnace slag.....	18
Characterizations of SiO ₂ -B ₂ O ₃ -Na ₂ O Amorphous Phase Separated Glasses	19
Analysis and comparison of hot forming technologies for complex 3D thin glass applications.....	20
High temperature optical properties of iron-doped silicate glasses and melts	21
Structural analysis of borophosphate glasses by 1D/2D NMR.....	22
Lubrication in glass production: Migrating your glass production from manual to fully automatic lubrication - potential routes and their pros and cons.....	23
Structural study of lanthanum aluminoborate glasses combining molecular dynamics, nuclear magnetic resonance and neutron diffraction.....	24
Sub-critical crack growth in hydrous silicate glasses.....	26
Deformation in borosilicate glass: densification or plastic flow?.....	27
Investigation of point defects generation in High Pressure/ High Temperature (HP-HT) densified silica under electron irradiation.	28
Structural study of binary alkaline-earth phosphate glasses by SVTD modeling and NMR and Raman spectroscopy	29
Local Deformation of Glasses is Mediated by Rigidity Fluctuation on Nanometer Scale.....	30
Understanding how microscale changes alter macroscale fracture properties in SiO ₂ -B ₂ O ₃ -Na ₂ O Glasses	31
Structural environments in oxide glasses SiO ₂ – Al ₂ O ₃ – La ₂ O ₃ by NMR and IR spectroscopies .	32
Heye International: IS Machine Blank Side Automation	33
Application of the model of associated solutions to the study of the structure and properties of Li ₂ O-P ₂ O ₅ glasses.....	34
Influence of Al addition on structure and mechanical properties of Borosilicate glass.....	35
Glass for Optics/Fibers / Laser Application on Glass	36
Innovative Laser Based Procedure for Deep Drawing of Three-Dimensional Glass Elements	37
Laser induced breakdown spectroscopy as a tool for determination of lead in recycled glass cullet	38
Sensors based on nanoparticles-doped optical fibers.....	39
Special functional glasses for the application in vacuum insulated materials	40

Influence of laser parameters on the densification of picosecond pulsed laser structured objects in silica glass.....	41
Modification of the europium environment by electron and femtosecond laser irradiation in metaphosphate and polyphosphate glasses	42
Wettability characteristics of hydrophobic and superhydrophobic glass surfaces by the combination of ultrafast lasers and sol-gel coatings	43
Micro lens arrays made by CO ₂ -laser radiation	44
Non silicate oxide glass compositions for laser writing and optical fibers	45
3D microchannels for tissue engineering in photosensitive glass using NIR femtosecond laser radiation	46
Structure and Properties of Gallium-Rich Germano-Gallate Glasses	47
Structural effects of laser induced filament formation in soda lime silicate glass and the impact on its direct vicinity	48
High-quality glass processing by means of ultrashort laser pulses	49
Side-emitting borosilicate glass fibers from modified rod-in-tube preforms.....	50
Optical properties of palladium-doped Sol-gel-derived ZrO ₂ thin films for multi-resonant surfaces .	51
Processing of soda lime silicate glass using Ultra-short-pulsed laser.....	52
Optical and chemical functionalities controlled at the micrometer scale in glassy materials by an imprinting thermo-electrical process.....	53
#N/A.....	54
Glasses in Healthcare.....	55
Bioactive glass nanoparticles for biomedical applications.....	56
Investigation of Surface Characteristics Before and After LASER Processing Dental Glass Ceramics	57
Silicate, borosilicate and borate bioactive glasses: A comparison of the dissolution behavior under different conditions.....	58
Effects of crystallisation on in vitro bioactivity in fluoride-containing bioactive glasses.....	59
Effect of TES buffer on the quality of hydroxyapatite formed on 45S5 based bioactive glass-ceramic scaffolds	61
Dissolution of phosphate glasses for therapeutic ion release: the effect of cobalt on hydrolysis.....	62
In vitro activity of ion-doped silicon oxycarbide-based bioactive glasses for bone tissue engineering	63
Micro and nano-sized glass particles for biomedical applications	64
Foam glass from cullet: some examples of study and applications	65
Application of high quality pharmaceutical glass for sensitive drug formulations.....	66
Thermodynamic - Redox - Color / Furnace, Energy and Environment	67
ECOPURE CATALYTIC CANDLE FILTER- Cost efficient partial flow DeNO _x solution	68
Operation data from OPTIMELT Heat Recovery System on a Tableware Glass Furnace at Libbey Leerdam	69
SORG hybrid for the glass industry	70
New Zircon Silicate refractory material for High Quality Glasses	71
Large lab-scale glass melting with hydrogen-oxygen combustion	72
Criticality of Accuracy and Traceability of Temperature Calibration	73
CO ₂ neutral glass production	74

Continuously measuring CO and O2 to optimize the combustion process	75
Glass Quality vs. Gas Quality? Results from the German Research Project „GasQualitaetGlas“ – Part I: Gas quality, the European situation and effects on the glass manufacturing process	76
In Situ investigation of melting Na2O-B2O3-SiO2 model glasses in continuous processes	77
Evaluation principle in respect of the batch melting zone of a glass melt furnace	78
Redox behavior of transient metals in glass: case of ruthenium in nuclear glass melt	79
Effect of network modifiers on redox and properties of iodine-bearing glasses	80
Evaluation and interpretation of tracer experiments performed on glass melters	81
Glass Quality vs. Gas Quality? Results from the German Research Project „GasQualitaetGlas“ (support code of the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy: 03ET1296(A to D))– Part II: Statistical analysis of local gas qualities and recommendations	82
DECOLORING OF AMBER COLOR	83
Spatial distribution of nucleated bubbles in molten glasses undergoing coalescence and growth ...	84
Redox state and coordination change of nickel ions in glasses	85
Options for step wise CO2 emission reduction.....	86
“All-Electric” Glass Manufacturing from a Power Supply Point of View.....	87
Irregular melting of the batch layer in the all-electric tank. Can drops be prevented	88
Heat Recovery Potential of the Glass Industry in Germany: practice	89
Heat Recovery Perspective of the Glass Industry in Germany: future options	90
Flakes, Spheres or Fibres? Influence of glass composition and process parameters on the glass particle morphology during centrifugal processing	91
Glass surface and alteration / coatings / Heritage	92
High performance AR-layers made from MgF2-sols	93
Characterization of PYREX® glass alteration in atmospheric condition	94
Understanding the browning phenomenon of medieval stained-glass windows: impact of bacteria and bacterial exudates on the dissolution of a Mn-bearing glass.....	95
PASSIVE FILLER LOADED POLYMER DERIVED GLASS/CERAMIC COATINGS ON AISI 441 STAINLESS STEEL SUBSTRATES.....	96
HIGH TEMPERATURE OXIDATION BEHAVIOUR OF PASSIVE FILLER LOADED POLYSILAZANE-DERIVED GLASS/CERAMIC COATING SYSTEMS ON AISI 441 STAINLESS STEEL.....	97
Final report on the DFG project: Phase-theory driven development of glasses and methods for the preparation of continuous protective glass layers on concrete.....	98
Reconstruction of historical mirrors in the Royal Palace of Dresden	99
Looking into the Atomic Structure of Ultrathin Glass Films	100
Monte Carlo Simulation of the Corrosion of Irradiated Simplified Nuclear Waste Glasses.....	101
Study of a Corrosion Process Using Model Historical Glasses.....	102
Influence of glass composition on vapor hydration of nuclear waste glasses	103
'Crystalline silicon from glass'	104
Temperature dependent mechanisms of the atmospheric alteration of a mix-alkali lime silicate glass	105
Preliminary results of Solid-state NMR analysis of phosphate glasses deposited as thin films.....	106
Mass production glass printing goes digital.....	107
The Age of Enlightenment, and the role that glass making played in it.....	108

Oriented surface crystallization in $18\text{BaO}\cdot 22\text{CaO}\cdot 60\text{SiO}_2$ and $\text{MgO}\cdot \text{CaO}\cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$ glasses	109
Structure and chemical durability of rapidly quenched borosilicate glass	110
A comparative study of Chemical Vapor Deposited SiO_2 thin films	111
Glass Ceramic / crystallization / nano and microtexturation	112
Investigation on the Influence of Electric Fields on the Crystallization Behavior of Glass Ceramics	113
Engineering of intergranular glass in ceramics, its characteristics and impact on the ceramic's properties	114
Creation and orientation by femtosecond laser irradiation of polar nanocrystals in silica-based glasses	115
The influence of glass structure on the precipitation and growth of nickel nanocrystals via redox-reaction with H_2 gas	116
Effect of variations in crystallization parameters on the phase transformations in pre-crystallized lithium silicate glass ceramics for dental application	117
Crystallization sequence in TiO_2 -nucleated glass ceramics with quartz solid solution, keatite solid solution and cordierite as main crystalline phases	118
Nucleation in $\text{BaO}\text{-SrO}\text{-ZnO}\text{-SiO}_2$ glasses provoked by metallic nanoparticles	119
Investigation of new compositions of $\text{ZrO}_2\text{-xGd}_2\text{O}_3$ thermal barrier coatings for mitigating CMAS effect	120
Compositional changes of sub-20-nm Er-doped phase-separated nanoparticles in silicates	121
DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES AND SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF AMORPHOUS SiO_2 NANOPARTICLES	122
Role of phosphorus in the nucleation of sodium aluminosilicate glasses	123
Study of the incorporation limit of iodine in borosilicate glass	124
Crystallization of sol-gel derived LAS solid solutions and their quartz inversion temperature	125
Heterogeneous nucleation of lithium disilicate melts supercooled with different speeds	126
Glass sintering with concurrent crystallization and foaming	127
Phase separation in borosilicate glasses investigated by using coupled Raman-Brillouin-DSC spectroscopy: spatial repartition and thermal effect	128
Vanadium-coloration during crystallization of $\text{Li}_2\text{O}\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$ glasses	129
Phase growth mechanism during late stages of microstructure formation in phase-separating sodium borosilicate glass	130
Local permittivities of borosilicate glasses containing RuO_2 particles	131
Crystallization of lanthanide-rich phases in glass-ceramics and glasses in relation with their composition and structure	132
Modeling from the atom to the final product : Process control, Data mining and Deep learning in the Glass Industry	133
Infrared temperature measurement in glass production	134
Glass Technology Development by Artificial Intelligence?	135
Modeling and simulation of nuclear glass synthesis	136
Energy Transfer in Glasses and Amorphous nanocomposites	137
Industry 4.0 and artificial intelligence for the glass industry	138
Spectral unmixing of Raman profiles relate structural heterogeneities to plastic flow in silicate glasses	139

Some constitutive models for silicate glasses elastoplasticity.....	140
Yield criterion developed from atomic-scale simulations and verified by micro-scale experiments	141
Sending products with total peace of mind.....	142
Multicomponent diffusion in industrial glasses and thin films.....	143
NMR Driven Reverse Monte Carlo Study of the Structure of Strontium-Aluminosilicate Glasses..	144
Mechanical property changes under irradiation in simplified nuclear glasses: a classical molecular dynamics study.....	145
Vertical Integration, basis for Production Boost and new ways of Production tuning.	146
Poster Session	147
Spontaneous breakage of toughened glass: About residual breakage risk after Heat-Soak Test..	148
Research Tools and Methodology for Waste Vitrification Process Development	149
EDX-analysis on medieval glasses and innovative protection of stained glass panels	151
Ligament, Cartilage and Skin Regeneration - Bioactive glass giving New Medical Applications....	152
Investigation on the influence of electric fields on the surface crystallization in LZAS glass ceramics	153
Multicomponent diffusion and structural modifications in Na ₂ O-CaO-Al ₂ O ₃ -SiO ₂ glasses and melts	154
Polarized Raman spectroscopy of ν -SiO ₂ under rare-gas compression.....	156
Effect of silicophosphate glass composition on structure and dissolution.....	157
Development of an in-situ method to determine the crystal growth kinetics in glass ceramics by measuring the elastic material properties.....	158
In-situ study of the ceramming of glasses by impedance spectroscopy	159
Titanium redox in crystals, glasses and melts	160
Manufacturing of complex shaped glass elements by application of a novel process chain	161
The effect of hydrostatic pressure on permanent glass densification, Raman- and luminescence-spectra of rare-earth-doped soda-lime-glass.....	162
Evaluation of the residual glass phase in fully crystallized dental lithium silicate glass ceramic. ...	163
High temperature synchrotron X-ray diffraction measurements of volcanic melt.....	164
Multicomponent mobility at the interface between glass and oxides thin layers	165
Preparation and characterization of bioactive coatings using sol-gel method.....	166
Fabrication of optical fiber glass preforms with zirconia coated gold nanoparticles.....	167
Fictive Temperature of fused silica	168
Crystallization of SiO ₂ -Polymorphs in multicomponent glasses of the system Li ₂ O-K ₂ O-MgO-Al ₂ O ₃ -SiO ₂ -P ₂ O ₅	169
Oriented surface crystallization in BT0.75S (fresnoite) glass under controlled conditions.....	170
Wave-Packet Propagation in Silicon Nano-Composite	171
Sintering of silver-glass composites	172
Subcritical crack growth in water-bearing soda-aluminosilicate glasses.....	173
Structural, thermal and optical study of binary Magnesium tellurite glasses.....	174
DEM&MELT In-Can Melting Technology for the Vitrification of Typical D&D Waste loaded with Cs	175
Atomistic insight into the mixed alkaline earth effect on the mechanical properties of metaphosphate glasses.....	176

Selective Laser Sintering of SiO ₂ Powder by high Temperature	177
Sub-critical crack growth in a silicate glass: Measurement vs. Simulation.....	178
Structural and optical characterization of alkali silicate thin films prepared by liquid route.....	179
A study on the economic production of porous glasses with lead oxide and lead containing waste glass.....	180
Operating limits for beam melting of glass materials.....	181
How does the substitution of Zn or Mg for Ca affect the thermal properties and the dissolution behaviour of Bioglass® 45S5?	182
Electro-optic glass based on antimony and silver doped PbO-Bi ₂ O ₃ -Ga ₂ O ₃ system - electro-optic characterization.....	183
Effects of microstructure on crack healing in glass matrix composites	184
Evolution of crystallization kinetics, and mineralization of partially crystallized 45S5 bioactive glass	185
Characterization of early crystallization stages in surface-crystallized diopside glass-ceramics	186
Boson peak, heterogeneity and intermediate-range order in binary SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃ glasses.....	187
Rheology of glasses out of their thermodynamic equilibrium, using dynamic methods	188
Luminescence-enhanced side-emitting fiber	189
Nano-indentation studies on curved glass fiber surfaces using different tip shapes.....	190
Leeching and dissolution phenomena of glass-ceramic sealed YSZ electrolyte.....	191

FunGlass

Sol-gel derived ion-doped mesoporous bioactive glasses for biomedical applications

PhD Zuzana Neščáková | Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín

Dr.-Ing. Liliana Liverani | Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nuremberg | DE

Dr.-Ing. Kai Zheng | University of Erlangen-Nuremberg | DE

PhD Martin Michálek | Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín

Prof. Dusan Galusek | FunGlass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin | SK

Prof. Aldo R Boccaccini | Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg | DE

zuzana.nescakova@tnuni.sk

Abstract

Bioactive glasses (BG) continue to attract interest for applications in bone tissue engineering because of their bioactive, osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties. Their application possibilities have covered also the area of soft tissue engineering and wound healing (1). The discovery of mesoporous bioactive glasses (MBG) opened a new direction for developing multifunctional bioactive materials by applying nanotechnology in regenerative medicine (2, 3). The main goal of the present work is the characterisation of SiO₂-CaO (MBG) and SiO₂-CaO-ZnO (MBG_Zn) bioactive glasses produced by the sol-gel route. The main feature of these nanosized SiO₂-based MBGs is the presence of a highly ordered mesoporous channel structure. The size of dispersed, spherical particles was in the range of 130 ± 10 nm. To connect the regenerative properties of MBGs with the beneficial effect of zinc, MBG doped with Zn²⁺ ions were successfully produced by using microemulsion assisted sol-gel method. EDS analyses and ICP_OES confirmed the presence of zinc in amount ~ 9 mol %. The designed material showed sustained released of zinc ions up to 21 days, reaching its maximum values after 14 days (1,12 mg/L). Cell culture tests with ST-2, MEF and MG-63 cell lines confirmed the cytocompatibility of the tested materials. SEM, XRD and FTIR indicated the formation of hydroxyapatite on the surface of MBG nanoparticles upon 3 days of immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF). On the other hand, the in vitro mineralization of MBG_Zn was markedly delayed confirming the same trend already reported in literature (4, 5) This fact can be considered an advantage in some applications such as wound dressing. These positive results confirm the suitability of the obtained MBG as candidates for biomedical applications.

Acknowledgement:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

References:

1. Miguez-Pacheco, V.; Hench, L.L.; Boccaccini, A.R. Bioactive glasses beyond bone and teeth: Emerging applications in contact with soft tissues. *Acta Biomater.* 2015, 13, 1-15.
2. X. Yan, C. Yu, X. Zhou, J. Tang, D. Zhao, Highly ordered mesoporous bioactive glasses with superior in vitro bone-forming bioactivities, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 2004, 43, 5980-5984.
3. Ch. Wu, Chang J., Multifunctional mesoporous bioactive glasses for effective delivery of therapeutic ions and drug/growth factors, *J. Con. Rel.* 2014, 193, 282-295.
4. Pérez, R.; Sanchez-Salcedo, S.; Lozano, D.; Heras, C.; Esbrit, P.; Vallet-Regí, M.; Salinas, A.J. Osteogenic effect of ZnO-mesoporous glasses loaded with osteostatin. *Nanomaterials* 2018, 8, 3-18.
5. Balasubramanian, P.; Strobel, L.A; Kneser, U.; Boccaccini, A.R. Zinc-containing bioactive glasses for bone regeneration, dental and orthopedic applications. *Biomed. Glasses* 2015, 1, 51-69.